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D7.1 Derivation of 10 germ-free mouse lines

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Introduction

This report compiles information about the axenic derivation or derivation of germ-free mice trans-national access (TNA) calls i.e., call overview, selected user projects, outcomes and outlook.

The main service providers involved were:

- Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS).
- Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian (FCG-IGC).
- Karolinska Institutet (KI).

The derivation of germ-free mice service was provided by three infrastructures with a long-standing expertise and track-record in the derivation of germ-free and gnotobiotic mice, namely the Gulbenkian GF Gnotobiology Unit, the Karolinska Institutet Core Facility for Germ-free Research, and the CNRS Service Isotechnie of the PHENOMIN/TAAM infrastructure. All infrastructures are partners and founding members of the ECGnoto network <http://www.ecgnoto.eu>.

All participating infrastructures are equipped with state-of-the-art autoclaves, IVC cages, cage washers, biosafety cabinets, and transfer and decontamination chambers. E.g. the Gulbenkian gnotobiology platform is equipped with germ-free isolators, and ISOTEC transfer chambers with connectors for strain axenization and cylinders for material extraction. For experimental work, isocage systems are used where each cage constitutes a single isolator, and biosafety cabinets are used to handle isocages and to manipulate mice for experiments under sterile conditions. The participating infrastructures are among very dedicated facilities in Europe who have the required equipment and expertise to generate germ-free and gnotobiotic mice. All infrastructures routinely offer their services to external users.

Unfortunately, the gnotobiology unite at KI ceased operations in December 2019 due to policy and financial constraints. However, the staff engaged in WP7 prioritized the remaining work schedule towards fulfilling WP7's goal of providing the 3 axenic lines (table 14). Staff involved in this work package were: Josefine Rosén (technician); Marta Panko (technician) and Velmurugesan Arulampalam (senior researcher).

Call Overview

Two WP7 call were published in July 2017 and December 2018 and successfully executed. The call information and documents related to WP5 can be accessed at: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/resources-and-services/axenic-service/infrafrontier-axenic-germ-free-service>

The TA service access unit covered the derivation of germ-free mice from a breeding nucleus or from frozen materials provided by the applicants. The infrastructures transferred and bred mice under SPF conditions, and then introduced and fostered 2 litters or 8 animals into one

germ-free isolator until 2 months of age. Tissues or body fluids were provided or arrangements were made for live germ-free shipments. Further breeding and characterisation of axenic mice or the development of gnotobiotic models were also offered on a fee-for-service or on a collaborative basis. Beyond the TA service provision, selected applicants were further assisted with logistics support and advice to ship back rederived germ-free mice to their facilities. Dedicated shippers were provided for transportation and specialised courier services were recommended.

In response to the WP7 calls a total of 13 eligible proposals were submitted, and 10 user projects and mouse models were selected for germ-free derivation. Project proposals were submitted from 8 countries, including a project proposal from Singapore. The review was based on short descriptions of the projects involving the germ-free mouse models that will be produced by the TA service. A mixed panel of members of INFRAFRONTIER service providers and network experts in the field of gnotobiology assessed service requests supported by the TA activity. In addition to scientific merit of applicants, the soundness of the proposal, relevance for microbiome research, and technical feasibility was assessed. For WP7, evaluations were carried out remotely but in addition evaluations were discussed among the selection committee members in person at one of the Gnotobiology Working Group meetings. Face to face discussions proved valuable to revise slightly evaluation criteria for the second call. Applicants were informed on the outcome of the evaluation within 6 weeks after the end of the call. All applications were handled with strict confidentiality.

Selected User Projects

Selected germ-free derivation projects - call 1

Production centre	Applicant	Project scope
Gulbenkian Institute Partner 25	Tagliabue Italy, Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori, Milan	Analyze the effect of eliminating gut bacteria in FVB-d16HER2 transgenic mice on tumor onset / multiplicity, and on tumor response to trastuzumab
Gulbenkian Institute Partner 25	Torrente Italy, University of Milan	Use germ-free mdx mice to investigate the impact of microflora on T cell production in a dystrophic environment and to develop new tools to improve the efficacy of clinical trials for degenerative diseases of skeletal muscle based on supplement diet and new microbiota-modulating drugs; evaluate the modulation of dystrophic phenotype associated to selected organisms (gnotobiotic mice) known to induce Th17 response or Treg production;
Gulbenkian Institute Partner 25	Terzic Croatia, University of Split	Understanding the physiological role of the immune system in bladder Discovering the nature of immune response in the bladder could lead to new strategies for prevention, management and treatment of urinary tract infections, as well as advances in immunotherapy for bladder cancer . The composition of the urinary microbiome and its possible link to various diseases of the urinary tract has been recently a focus of the scientific community. Here we would like to study the differences in the transcriptome profile in the bladder of C57BL/6 mice housed in axenic and SPF conditions. Expression profiles could reveal how urothelial and resident immune cells are modulated by the presence of microbes and microbial products.
PHENOMIN-TAAM (CNRS) Partner 18	Singh Germany, University of Tübingen	Understand how the gut microbiome can drive immune cell activation and lead to Parkinsons Disease pathology

PHENOMIN-TAAM (CNRS) Partner 18	Lantz France, Institut Curie, Paris	Generation of germ-free B6-MAITCast mice for the study of MAIT (Mucosal Associated Invariant T cells) cell development
Karolinska Institute Partner 26	Desseyn France, INSERM University of Lille	Mucus is the first protective barrier of the mucosal surface. It plays a crucial role as a selective barrier and gatekeeper against unwanted bacteria to interact with the underlining epithelium. Abnormal mucus is a key feature in inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD) where the intestinal mucus is less protective against the endogenous microflora. The aim of this project is to determine if the observed intestinal mucus strengthening of the knock-in Tg222 line depends of the microbiota.
Karolinska Institute Partner 26	Singaraja Singapore, National University of Singapore	The overall goal of the proposed project is to investigate the role of the microbiome on bile acid pool composition, improved glucose metabolism, insulin resistance and insulin secretion observed in mice with a targeted deletion in the bile acid gene, Cyp8b1.

Selected germ-free derivation projects – call 2

Production centre	Applicant	Project scope
Gulbenkian Institute Partner 25	Wullaert Belgium, University of Ghent	In this project, we propose to rederive our unique NLRC4V341A mouse model of NLRC4-driven auto-inflammatory disease into germ-free conditions in order to identify the endogenous triggers responsible for eliciting overproduction of IL-18 that drives pathology in these rare genetic disorders in humans. Rederiving the NLRC4V341A/V341A mouse line into GF conditions is the only way to completely eliminate the bacterial, viral and fungal communities residing in the intestine and thus to unequivocally show the collective contribution of these gut microbiota in eliciting IL-18 in these mice.

<p>PHENOMIN-TAAM (CNRS) Partner 18</p>	<p>Jabs France, Institut Pasteur, Paris Braulke Germany, University Medical Center Hamburg Eppendorf</p>	<p>Role of the microbiota in the pathogenesis of the neurodegenerative amino acid degradation disorder glutaric aciduria Type 1 (GA1) GA1 is a rare and severe neurodegenerative disease characterized by a wide spectrum of clinical symptoms caused by the deficiency of the mitochondrial enzyme glutaryl-CoA-dehydrogenase (GCDH). GCDH is involved in the degradation pathway of the amino acids lysine and tryptophan. Clinical manifestation occurs typically between 6 and 36 months of life triggered by catabolic conditions e.g. intercurrent illness, infection, or vaccination, leading to encephalopathic crisis with selective irreversible striatal injury, and subdural hematomas followed by movement disorder, and increased morbidity. This application is based on our hypothesis that developmentally-regulated changes in the gut flora of 6-36 months old GA1 patients play a previously unrecognized role in timing and onset of the disease, the pattern of striatal injury and the outcome following encephalopathic crisis triggered by catabolic conditions. We will test whether fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) or alterations in the gut microbiome of GCDH KO mice can be used as new therapeutic intervention to interfere with or avoid the course of diet-induced encephalopathic crisis as proof-of-principle.</p>
<p>Karolinska Institute Partner 26</p>	<p>Poutanen Finland, University of Turku</p>	<p>Modeling the impact of microbiota on the devastating outcome of estrogen exposure on males In previous studies the applicant has shown that male mice universally expressing human aromatase enzyme (AROM+), and thus having increased conversion of androgens to estrogens, are feminized and present with severe disorders in their reproductive organs. New preliminary data show that intestinal microbiota of young adult (2-month old) AROM+ males is altered, and it resembles more the microbiota of WT females. Treatment with aromatase inhibitor shifted the microbiota composition of the AROM+ males more to the WT male-resembling microbiota, supporting the role of sex steroids in the modification of the microbiota. Thus, our preliminary data indicate that the hormonal changes present in the AROM+ males interact with the microbiome. The specific questions in the proposed pilot study are: 1. Do the microbiota contribute, and how, to the estrogenized phenotype of AROM+ mice?</p>

		2. Has the intestinal microbiota a role in the regulation of lipid metabolism and/or humoral immunity by sex steroids?
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Summary of Tasks from KI in WP 7

Project Applicant			Derivation			Shipping		Notes
Name	Country	Mouse line	Number of Times	Date of Completion	Breeding Post derivation	Final Destination	Date	
Roshni Singaraja	Singapore	Cyp8bKO	8	March-April 2019	Yes	IGC, Lisbon, Portugal	17-18 Dec 2019	Need cholate-supplemented chow for breeding under germ free conditions. Transferred to the WP7 partner in Portugal.
Matti Poutanen	Finland	AROM+	4	May 2019	No	Turku University, Finland.	7-8 October 2019	-
Jean-Luc Desseyn	France	Tg-222 Knock-In	4	April 2019	No	Institut Pasteur de Lille, France	2-3 July 2019	Further experiments and axenic assessment will be done in Institut Pasteur de Lille

Outcomes

Researcher Name	User Project	Short Name	Status	Remarks
Yogesh Singh	DJ-1	CNRS	Cancelled	Cancelled as strain was lost by the user
Olivier Lantz	MAIT	CNRS	Ongoing	Obtained first germ-free mice and the breeding is ongoing.
Sabrina Jabs	GA1	CNRS	Ongoing	Obtained germ-free mice. The breeding is ongoing and have first newborns.
Elda Tagliabue	ERBB2	FCG-IGC	Completed	
Yvan Torrente	DMD	FCG-IGC	Completed	
Andy Wullaert	NLRC4	FCG-IGC	Completed	
Janos Terzic	Bladder	FCG-IGC	Completed	
Jean Luc Desseyn	Tg222	KI	Completed	
Roshni Singaraja	Cyp8b1	KI	Completed	
Matti Poutanen	AROM	KI	Completed	

User Feedback

User	Satisfied with the service?	Pay a competitive price (non-profit) for the same service?	Any publications in preparations?	Feedback Remarks
Andy Wullaert	Yes	Yes	Not yet	The service showed great flexibility given the difficult pandemic circumstances!
Elda Tagliabue	Yes	Maybe	Not yet	Seriousness and competence in every aspect of the service provided
Roshni Singaraja	Yes	No	Not yet	Very helpful program leads at the germ-free mouse program. Successfully generated germ-free mice.

Service Analysis: Troubleshooting, Hidden Costs and Outlook

Troubleshooting and Problems

- High risk of contaminations. However, users usually understand the risk of contaminations
- Some animal procedures may be very difficult to execute in axenic conditions (complex surgeries for instance)
- Specificity of the projects allow the improvement and development of new SOPs

Hidden Costs

- Contaminations
- Equipment repairs
- Equipment depreciation

Beyond TA Calls

Elda Tagliabue, ERBB2

- Maintenance of the axenic colony for several months to assess the role of the microbiota in the efficacy of a drug treatment in a breast-tumor transgenic model.
- Experiments consisted of administrating the drug in axenic mice and to follow-up tumor development.
- Project concluded successfully.
- Constant communication with the users by e-mail, Zoom.

Yvan Torrente, DMD

- Production of more axenic animals to do further experiments.
- In the process of shipping the axenic mice to the user.
- Constant communication with the users by e-mail.

Roshni Singaraja, Cyp8b1

- Maintenance of the axenic colony for several months to do experiments on metabolism (insulin resistance and insulin secretion observed in axenic mice with a targeted mutation in the bile acid gene Cyp8b1).
- Experiments started but meanwhile, the project was cancelled by the user because the PI moved to another Institute and no lab personnel was available to proceed.
- Constant communication with the users by e-mail, Zoom.

Outlook

- Possibility of providing services beyond the TA call in a fee-for-service or on a collaborative basis
- Projects were scientifically sound and technically viable

- Researchers were understanding when there were problems (contaminations that delayed the conclusion of the project)
- Involve private companies and enterprises (e.g., suppliers). This could open new avenues of funding and new markets
- Enlarge visibility and networks via INFRAFRONTIER communication activities
- Explore more international and national funding opportunities. For example, FCG-IGC have included GF/Gnoto in CONGENTO, a PT RI part of the National Roadmap

Future of INFRAFRONTIER Axenic Service

Offering axenic derivation as a TA call or on a fee-for-service basis is promising as there is a growing need for this service. This is evident by large demand experienced by the service providers and a PubMed search on microbiota shown below. This service is expensive to establish and maintain, requiring specialised scientific expertise for proper execution. It is very common that researchers cannot afford the derivation of new mouse strains to axenic conditions. This may discourage the usage of this powerful technology, impeding new discoveries in the role of the microbiota in health and disease. Given this economic constrain, availability of funding opportunities is especially crucial in this field of research.

Shown below are survey results of INFRAFRONTIER partners capable of offering axenic services. The survey inquired about their axenic services, current issues in the field that need discussion, their willingness to participate in future TA calls and offer services on a fee-for-service basis.

Name	Institute and country	Axenic services or gnotobiology research in general	Open issues that need discussion	Offer axenic services as an INFRAFRONTIER service	Offer axenic services as a TA calls
Marion Berard	Institut Pasteur France	Generation of new axenic mouse lines, Breeding of axenic and gnotoxenic mouse lines, Implementation of experimental procedures on mouse lines	Access to commercial mouse and rat lines	Yes	Yes
Martin Fray	MRC-Harwell	We are in the process of re-establishing our germ-free capability in the hope that we can establish a National germ-free facility. Plans are being prepared for a new animal house (the National Centre for Pre-clinical Innovation) which will have substantial germ free and microbiome study holding facilities	Transporting gnoto mice and efficient rederivation procedures	Yes	Yes
Manuel Rebelo	Instituto Gulbenkian de Ciência, Portugal	Axenic Facility: total capacity of 8 isolators (140 mouse cages in total) Gnotobiology Facility: total capacity for 142 experimental mouse cages.	FUNDING; advertisement of the Service; benchmarking (how many facilities in Europe, prices).	Yes	Yes
Reetta Hinttala/Reetta Vuolteenaho	University of Oulu, Finland	Small-scale germfree facility will be established together with Laboratory Animal Centre. Isocage system (30 cages) and changing station were purchased in 2020. The operation is in the establishment stage.	Practical training and site visits as soon as pandemics situation allows, funding for technical personnel, further funding for equipment		

Yann Herault	Phenomin	Full service available	Definition of axenisation	Yes	Yes
Cecile Fremond	CNRS TAAM Phenomin France	Production of GF and GX mice lines	Health monitoring standardisation for GF mice	Yes	Yes

The possibilities to offer axenic and gnotobiont biology services as TA calls or as paid services was followed up with the above partners in the final Gnotobiont WG meeting held virtually on 9th March 2021. All service providers were in favour of offering their services as TA calls but held reservations about offering them on a fee-for-service basis as the germ-free incubators are always in high demand and need to be reserved well in advance. Empty incubators would imply a huge cost burden in case users are not willing to pay for the service.

Owing to the success of the axenic service TA calls in I2020 and previous INFRAFRONTIER projects like INFRAFRONTIER-I3, FCG-IGC have offered a similar service with additional tumour studies under the HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01 call aimed to study the relationship between cancer and gut microbiota. In addition, **FCG-IGC will also offer their service on a fee-for-service basis as the INFRAFRONTIER axenic derivation service that will be prominently showcased on the new INFRAFRONTIER website.**